

Recommended citation: Sipos, B., Oláh, T., Széles, K., Balogh, J., & Szilágyi, B. (2021). How to utilize test results effectively. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 509-517). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14647085.

HOW TO UTILIZE TEST RESULTS EFFECTIVELY?

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Conference Key Areas: *Mathematics in engineering, Digital tools*

Keywords: *complex mathematical and grammatical test, engineering students*

ABSTRACT

There are numerous ways in which universities measure their first years' abilities essential to begin one of our courses. Institutions try to define processes, which projects successful progress or drop-out rates.

To create such tests is no easy task. In recent years, one of our research groups has developed complex mathematical and grammatical tests, which have been completed by more than a hundred students. In our experience, students are conditioned to a certain type of standardized test, since they can practice on the previous years' tests. Hence the results become distorted. However, we find that a greater knowledge is required for grammatical tests, thus the results tend to be more accurate. Standardized tests are much easier to predict.

First year engineers at BME have written several tests. The van Hiele test, which measures geometrical thinking, a university-required test that assesses their knowledge of calculus, and our afore-mentioned test. In our research we analyzed and compared the results. We could see that the students, who did well in our test, also did well in calculus. Furthermore, we found that there is a correlation between the results of mathematical and grammatical tests.

To summarize, with the results compared, we could see a clearer picture of the abilities of our freshmen. Which is incredibly important during a pandemic, where our contact with the students is limited.

1 INTRODUCTION

Students entering their university studies write entrance tests at many universities around the world, even though they have been admitted as part of an admissions process. Multiple tests can serve different purposes. Some of them examine the existence of the knowledge needed to complete a course, others try to find an answer to how successful the student will be in the future, whether there is a risk of dropping out. The latter is really high in the fields of Science Technology Engineering Mathematics (STEM) all around Europe, which causes a shortage of manpower, as the dynamic development of these fields requires an increasing number of engineers, computer scientists and scientists.

Marcell Nagy and Roland Molontay analyzed the data of the students of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (21,547 people) using statistical learning methods to examine the strength of the admission points of the students in the Hungarian admission procedure. They prove that grades from high school have a strong predictive force, furthermore the general knowledge is more important than program-specific knowledge. They also find that the academic performance of the males is overpredicted, however, that of females is underpredicted by the university entrance score system [1].

1.1 Admission and testing of freshmen during pandemia

Due to a pandemic starting in China at the end of 2019, the students who had their admission in September 2020, closed their high school studies under changed circumstances. The last academic year of high school, the most important period in terms of repetition, synthesis of the learned material, and final exams, has already been spent in online education. In Hungary, only written final examinations were held, with the exception of a few subjects. There were no oral exams in mathematics, physics or computer science, although they were particularly relevant for further engineering studies at Budapest University of Technology and Economics.

In September 2020, the freshmen students began their studies in hybrid education, the large number of lectures were held online, while the practices were taught in attendance. After a few weeks, due to the aggravation of the epidemic situation, full education continued online. The so-called 'Zero exam' which is a necessary condition for fulfilling the object of calculation, was performed in such circumstances. This exam is compiled by the lecturers of the Institute of Mathematics of BME and is uniform in all faculties, the tasks are freely available for several years [2]. However, we find that these tests have traditionally performed well in the population we studied (first-year mechatronic and energetic students), with nearly no failed performers. The results of this measurement do not show a relationship with the success of completing the calculus subject, and they are not suitable for screening talented students. We suspect that those students, who are also outstanding in the field of engineering, learn relatively easily the type of the tasks of the zero exam, but only the existence of the most basic knowledge can be measured with this, even though the fulfilment of engineering subjects would require the ability to apply what has been learned in the

subject of calculus. The knowledge acquired there, is safely applied in the problems that arise in the further engineering subjects. A zero exam- type survey does not aim to answer more complex questions (for example, how effective is the formation of groups if we want to implement differentiated education later). In this way, only the existence of basic skills and abilities is checked, and the excellent performance on it is not a guarantee for further excellence.

1.2 Motivation and goals

The question arises as to whether there is a way to learn more from the results of a survey at the beginning of the first year. If we intend to write this type of test, we should avoid being able to “be prepared in double-quick” knowing the tests of previous years and not to shock students with the poor results of an exam written in the first week, for whom mathematics will not play an important role in the future either. Such testing is designed with the intention of helping students at the university to continue on a career path that is as wide-ranging as possible according to their abilities. Our research team developed a test a few years ago, which is presented below, that includes a set of language tasks in addition to mathematics. Since then, we have completed the test with hundreds of first-year students of technical or economic fields of higher education. We have found that a new, modern competency test method has been developed that gives a prediction of the performance of first-year students at the time of their entry to the university with excellent accuracy and helps the identification of students who need more catch-up or talent management [3].

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 University selection procedure in Hungary

In Hungary, the university selection procedure is partly similar to that of other Central and Eastern European countries. Students complete a nationally uniform matriculation examination at the end of high school. The exam subjects are Hungarian language and literature, mathematics, history, a foreign language, and an elective subject. Each higher education institution defines the elective subjects for its selection procedure. In technical higher education, these subjects are typically physics, informatics or chemistry. The purpose of the matura exam is to check the existence of the required knowledge for the chosen university education program. Matura exam can be taken at an advanced or intermediate level in any subject. Each university determines the advanced level graduation subjects required for admission. From 2020, all students continuing higher education in Hungary are required to take at least one subject at an advanced level. The results of the matura exam are converted into points. A maximum of 200 points can be obtained from the graduation results, another 200 points are earned for grades from the last two years of high school. An additional up to 100 extra points can be obtained for advanced level matura exams relevant to university studies, for results achieved in study, art, and sports competitions, and for language exams. Like the Swedish model, students who perform well at graduation but have low scores from their high school studies can double their graduation points.

2.2 Investigated group

The students in our study population were admitted to two majors with the highest admission scores of the leading technical institution in Hungary. In 2020, the 433 points was for mechatronics, 349 points for energy engineering was the inclusion point limit [4]. The average admission score of the mechatronics in our study population is 459 points and 421.5 points for energy engineering students. A large proportion of students came from a high school where they studied mathematics or science subjects in a higher number of hours. This ratio is 51.6% (32 students) for energy engineering students and 51.1% (47 students) for mechatronic students. 59 (64.1%) of the mechatronics students and 41 (66.1%) of the energy engineering students graduated in advanced level from mathematics.

2.3 Description of the test

Language and mathematics are thought by many to be two very different areas. However, the situation cannot be so polarized. At a basic level, we can make many connections between language and mathematics. Our test is formed by two large parts (linguistic and mathematical), which also contain tasks that are unusual for Hungarian students, with the help of which students with knowledge deficits of certain types of tasks can be screened out.

The Hungarian language task series - related to mathematics - not only measured language knowledge, but also tried to explore the mechanisms of thinking. We used the elements learned in general and secondary education, but the tasks primarily required the application of learned knowledge.

The test took 70 minutes. It is also important that the student is able to complete the task in a timely manner, so the tests were designed to perform all tasks with only the expected speed. The test contains several examples, for which the solution takes longer time with using template methods, while a deeper understanding of the problem provides a much shorter path to success.

The test contained 14 multiple choice mathematical exercises, each with 4 possible answers from which only one was correct. The tests (basic and advanced) were divided into three blocks. The task types are shown in the table below.

Requested knowledge	Procedural skills	Difficulty (1-5)
Mechanical calculation skills	Operations with fractions	1
	Calculations related to absolute value	1
	Exponential Expressions	1
Combined mechanical calculation skills	Logarithms exponentials and square roots	2
Applying mechanical calculation skills in an unknown environment	Breaking into partial fractions	3
Application of learned functional knowledge	Calculations of the value set of a function	2
Slightly unusual application of learned functional knowledge	Knowledge of the substitution value of a function	3
Slightly unusual examination of learned knowledge	Calculations of polynomial roots	3
Basic relations	Logic, knowledge of relations	4

Slightly unusual application of learned knowledge under general conditions	Function transformation	4
Unusual environment	Proportional thinking	5
	Function graph - formula relationship	5
Difficult, complex, unusual	Parametric geometric problem	5

Table 1. Math test tasks by type and difficulty

The first block (Block 1), containing the first four exercises in basic and the first five exercises in advanced level, controlled the basic, procedural computing knowledge. Fillers had to be accounted for their degree of familiarity with power, their identities, their confidence in logarithmic expressions, and their understanding of basic functional concepts. Our first hypothesis was that the fulfilment of these tasks (at least 60%) was a necessary condition not only for Calculus 1, but also for subjects requiring mathematical knowledge.

The second block (exercises 5-10) contained slightly more difficult tasks compared to Block 1. Here we tried to map the existence of important knowledge for later studies like Calculus. Compared to the tasks in Block 1, there were more complex examples that were set in the form known from high school including geometric, functional knowledge and logical statements. Our second hypothesis was that those who solved at least 6 tasks from Blocks 1-2 (i.e., exercises 1-10) will be able to complete the harder subject with good results, while others might have some trouble with the math-based subjects in the first academic year.

The last block (Block 3) contained unusual tasks that could only be solved by students having profound knowledge from high school and who are able to apply it while solving unexpected exercises for them. To solve the tasks of this block, the highest level of abstraction was needed, for example, there was a parametric geometry task, for which an understanding of functions was also needed for the correct solution.

The tasks of the language test cover a relatively wide range of procedural skills. In addition to the knowledge of grammatical elements, they affect several areas of linguistic abstraction: text correction, logical thinking, meaning identifications of text elements, interpretation of text structure, analogical thinking, rule recognition. The application of skill-level thinking mechanism (analysis, synthesis etc.) in the educational process, the incorporation of learned knowledge is closely related to the cultural and age characteristics of the relationship with the language.

Requested knowledge	Procedural skills	Difficulty (1-5)
a) text correction b) recognition of statements	a) Grammatical elements b) Comprehension	4
a) synonymy and b) circumscription	a) Lexical knowledge, passive vocabulary and b) Identification	4
Word recognition, basics of grammar, meaning identification (12 MC question)	Word development, synthesis, language skills, identification	3
word-syllable distinction (5 pcs)	Word development, syllables	2
meaning of verbs conjugation	semantics of verbs	5
Creation of word structures	analogy, linguistic abstraction	4
Word formation	synthesizing thinking	4
interpretation of foreign language elements	language analysis, systems theory	4
Style theory	comprehension, style knowledge	5
Interpretation of word element meaning	analytical ability	4

comprehension, sentence formation	comprehension, analysis of language elements	5
Comprehension of literary text, interpretation of style marks	comprehension of text, understanding of style	5
Text comprehension, logical connections	text value, reproducibility	5
Graph interpretation	visual ability, logical ability	3

Table 2. Language test tasks by type and difficulty

We measured the skill-level application of learned language, grammar, and mathematics. We set the measurement levels of Hungarian language and mathematical skills to each other (knowledge transfer, abstraction skills, etc.). We had to cross over to the usual school task schemes, we had to generate new task situations. We were looking for connection segments between language and mathematics that require similar or identical application of knowledge and ability. We placed skill-level knowledge in an unusual problem situation because we assumed higher thinking skills. Higher levels of text abstraction, rule recognition, language synthesis, difficult utilization of words, and meaning identification were mixed with simpler task problems.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Comparison of test results

Fig. 1 shows the results of each student. The earned points by solving comprehension problems are plotted as a function of the results reached in the mathematical part of the test. It is clearly visible that there are some students whose poor comprehension score is coupled with a good math test score. However, we did not find a student who had performed well in the comprehension part of the test but got poor results in mathematics. Being “elite” students, there were only two of them who performed poorly in both parts.

Fig. 1. Comparison of Math and Language test results

Fig. 2. Comparison of test results for students taking advanced level examination and attended advanced math classes

Figs. 2 shows the results reached on the language-mathematics test as a function of the results obtained on the zero math test. The blue dot indicates the ones who had a math final exam in an advanced level, while the orange dots correspond to the ones taking the final exam in the middle/normal level. The size of the dot is larger if more students have achieved the same result. The figure (B) below also shows the results obtained on the language-mathematics test as a function of the results reached on the zero math test. The blue dot now indicates those who were in math or science faculty, while the orange indicates the complement. The size of the dot is proportional to the length of the learning.

Note that both figures have a shape of an “upper triangle”, namely most of the students are located above the diagonal connecting the upper left corner of the rectangle to the lower right. This refers to the fact that the two figures are not different essentially.

Fig. 3. Comparison of test results for students taking advanced level examination and attended advanced math classes

The zero math test is intended to check the existence of the level of knowledge required for the successful completion of the calculus course. If we examine the results of the two midterm exams written in the semester as a function of the score reached on the zero exam, in both cases, the points are rather below the diagonal connecting the lower left and upper right vertices of the rectangle which refers to the fact that the two measurements are not independent (Fig. 3). However, a good zero math test does not necessarily mean successful performance yet, but a weak zero math test is rarely followed by a good calculus result. The markings are similar to the previous figures.

Fig. 4 shows the results obtained in the complex test as a function of the mark obtained from the calculus subject, both in the linguistic and mathematical part. The obtained results are presented divided by the maxima. It is clear that the more unusual, novel task (language test) was more difficult for the students. It can also be seen from the figure that weaker scores resulted weaker calculus grades; this relationship was stronger in the case of the language test. The number of students having great results in math tests, although performing poorly in calculus courses is only a few, who obtained bad results in the language test.

Fig. 4. Comparison of test results and the grade of Calculus 1

4 CONCLUSION

The multiple tests we use to measure first-year students provide us information from different aspects. The complex language-math test is more predictive than the one containing only math tasks, so it can be used effectively to measure first-year students. New types of impressions can shed light on connections which cannot be or only difficult to extract by other methods.

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